

EFFECT OF FIBER ORIENTATION ON DEFORMATION

AND FRACTURE OF Mg/B COMPOSITES

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Diffusion bonded composites consisting of magnesium - 10% volume fraction of boron fibers, aligned at 0° , 90° , $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ to the specimen axis, were deformed in uniaxial tension. The 0° specimens showed the highest strength levels, the 90° specimens the lowest, while the $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens showed strengths intermediary between those of 0° and 90° . In the 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens the matrix deformation was conspicuously concentrated in the vicinity of the fibers. The fracture path in the 0° specimens was approximately normal to the tensile axis. There occurred multiple fiber fracture and fiber pull out. In 90° specimens, the fracture started always parallel to the transverse fibers by separation along the fiber/matrix interface. Practically no fiber breakage occurred. In $0^\circ - 90^\circ$, the fracture process appeared to be a mixture of the above two. There was practically no interaction between the two sets of fibers. In the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens the fracture invariably ran parallel to either one or both the sets of fibers, accompanied by some fiber fracture and a lot of tearing of matrix between the two sets of fibers. These results are explained in terms of the state of stress existing in these composites when tested in uniaxial tension.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites are highly anisotropic; the best performance being, generally, obtainable in the direction of the fibers. Thus, one finds that the most efficient manner of utilizing a fiber composite is to have fibers aligned parallel to the loading direction. However, most structures in real life have multiple load paths which makes it imperative to understand how fiber orientation with respect to the applied stress affects the composite performance. This study was concerned with deformation and fracture behavior of diffusion bonded composites consisting of magnesium - 10% volume fraction boron fibers, aligned at 0° , 90° , $0^\circ - 90^\circ$, and $\pm 45^\circ$ to the specimen axis, under uniaxial applied tension. The composites were produced commercially and as such the present study also serves as a state-of-the-art characterization of the commercially produced metal matrix composites.

Experimental

The composite material was obtained in the form of 2.5 mm thick sheets. There were 14 layers of boron fibers. The $\pm 45^\circ$ composite, as the designation indicates, had boron fibers in a cross ply arrangement. In the $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ composite, boron fibers had 0° and 90° orientations in alternate layers. The boron fibers were 145 μm in diameter. The composites were commercially manufactured by the diffusion bonding process wherein alternate layers of boron fibers and magnesium foils are enclosed in an envelope and hot pressed. The amount and duration of the pressure and the temperature are critical parameters. Exact fabrication conditions could not be ascertained. These diffusion bonded composites, generally, have matrix/matrix interfaces, in addition to the fiber/matrix interfaces. The matrix material was of commercial purity (grain size: 0.74 mm). Its chemical analysis is given in Table I. Tensile specimens were cut from these sheets by electro discharge machining. Tensile testing was carried out in an Instron (TT-DM) machine at a cross head speed of 0.05 cm/min at room temperature. The deformation was measured by an Instron clip-on type extensometer. The sensitivity of elongation measurement was 1.25×10^{-4} cm. Optical and scanning electron microscopes were used to examine the composite microstructures at various stages.

TABLE I
Chemical analysis of magnesium matrix

Element	Al	Fe	Cu	Zn	Si	Mg
Wt. %	0.520	0.09	0.007	0.031	0.097	rest

Results

The representative stress strain curves of the four types of composites used in this work are shown in Fig.1. The 0° specimens showed, as expected, the highest stress levels; followed by $0^\circ - 90^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° specimens. The $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens showed the maximum elongation while the 0° specimens showed the minimum. As the straining proceeded, 'clicks' indicating fiber breaks could be heard, especially in the 0° specimens. This was further confirmed by the presence of multiple fiber fracture as revealed by metallographic examination.

The fracture of a 0° specimen is shown in Fig.2, a scanning electron micrograph. Notice the extensive fiber pull out. That the fiber/matrix bonding was quite variable can be seen from the fact that the central fiber in this photomicrograph has adhering to it a sizeable piece of magnesium which has teared off from the matrix. The surface of magnesium matrix against which the fiber slides during pull out became quite rough and torn. This can be seen in the scanning electron micrograph shown in Fig.3. An examination of fiber surface showed magnesium particles sticking on its surface.

The stress strain curves of 90° specimens showed the low performance level of these specimens. The matrix deformation was concentrated in the vicinity of fibers. Fiber/matrix interface decohesion occurred as a rule which, virtually, left the magnesium foils to undergo the rest of the tension test in isolation. Fig. 4a depicts this while Fig. 4b shows that occasionally the fiber matrix bond was strong enough along a part of the fiber length to pull the matrix down and start a crack in the matrix. This is similar to the behavior noticed in 0° specimens as indicated in Fig.2. The fracture surface ran more or less parallel to the transverse fibers with an occasional stretch, where Mg/Mg separation had occurred, running parallel to the applied stress axis.

The $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ specimens exhibited behavior

intermediate between that of 0° and 90° specimens. Their ultimate tensile strength was midway between the 0° and 90° specimens as was their elongation to fracture (See Fig.1). The fracture surface ran mostly parallel to the 90° fibers with small stretches along the 0° fibers. This is shown in Fig.5 (scanning electron micrograph). Complete fiber/matrix decohesion along the interface occurred only in fibers which were at 90° to the tensile axis. Partial decohesion at fiber breaking points leading to fiber pull out occurred in the fibers which were at 0° to the tensile axis. This is shown in Fig.6 (scanning electron micrograph). Some fiber splitting can also be seen. There was, thus, practically no interaction between the two sets of fibers.

The $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens showed very interesting results. The most prominent feature of their behavior was that the matrix deformed in shear parallel to the two sets of fibers which were oriented mutually at right angles but at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the applied stress axis. An evidence of this shear is seen in Fig.7, an optical micrograph. Notice the two scratch marks on the magnesium matrix surface; these marks have been displaced by the shear of the matrix along the direction of one of the fibers. Cracking has started in the matrix along the fiber direction. At the same time there was a tendency for the matrix to deform by shear along the other fiber direction which was at right angles to the first one. This shear of magnesium matrix along the two fiber directions led to a characteristic quasi-rectangular void formation in the matrix with the long side of the rectangle being parallel to that fiber direction along which the first shear deformation started. This is depicted vividly in Fig.8 (SEM). It would appear that some openings or microvoids formed in the matrix along the length of the fiber which were later transformed into quasi-rectangular voids by the pull on the matrix along the two fiber directions. Similar effect has been observed previously in $\pm 45^\circ$ Al/Borsic (1). The tearing of matrix between the two sets of fibers is further shown in Fig.9 where one can see that the matrix has cracked along one set of fibers and the strip of matrix has then been pulled along the complementary set of fibers. The final fracture generally ran part way along one set of fibers and part way along the other. This is shown in Fig.10, another scanning micrograph.

An important observation with regard to the matrix deformation concerns the amount of mechanical twinning. The magnesium matrix in the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens was marked by an extraordinarily high incidence of twinning vis a vis that in any other type.

Discussion

Several investigations (2-5) of fiber orientation effects have been made. According to the Kelly and Davies (3) formulation of expressions for off-angle behavior of composites, originally derived by Stowell and Liu (2), there are three independently operating failure modes depending on the fiber orientation:

1. at low angles, close to 0° , fiber tensile failure leads to composite failure.
2. at high angles, close to 90° , interface or matrix plane strain tensile failure causes composite failure.
3. at intermediate angles, matrix shear failure is responsible for composite failure.

As we shall see below, the behavior of commercially produced Mg/B composites bears out the above analysis i.e. deformation and failure modes shown are those that one would expect from the above analysis.

Boron fibers are quite brittle and have variable strain at fracture. 'Clicks' indicating fiber snapping during tensile testing could be heard, especially in the 0° specimens. This means that the first fiber breaks occurred at relatively low stress levels. Examination of the samples after failure showed multiple fracture of boron fibers and matrix cracking did not appear to be related to fiber snapping points. Thus, it would appear that with increasing applied stress, these initial fiber breaks, in general, did not lead to crack propagation in the matrix. Instead, there occurred localised bond failure between the matrix and the fiber at these sites and the consequent fiber pull out. An accumulation of fiber snaps throughout the specimen and fiber pull out led to an extreme weakening of one cross section of the composite and the failure ensued at that cross section. This would be the description of the fracture mode of the 0° specimens.

In the 90° specimens, the ultimate stress was about one half while the strain at fracture was only a little more than that of 0° specimens. The fracture mode, generally, involved fiber/matrix interface separation followed by tensile failure of the matrix foils. Fiber splitting was rare which means that fiber/matrix interface was not particularly strong in these commercially made composites. Fiber/matrix interface was the weak link and the composite failure occurred there which is in accord with the above mentioned analysis. Occasionally, matrix/matrix interface joining two transverse fibers opened up, but only after the

occurrence of fiber/matrix decohesion.

In the $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ specimens, the 10% volume fraction of fibers being distributed half and half along 0° and 90° , the performance was midway between the 0° and 90° samples. The failure modes were also a mixture of those encountered in 0° and 90° specimens. The fracture path zig-zagged along 0° and 90° (see Fig.5). Pull out of the fibers at 0° , fiber/matrix interface debonding and occasional fiber splitting of the fibers at 90° occurred practically as they would have in one type of reinforcement in the absence of the other. That is to say that to a first approximation there was no interaction between the two sets of fibers at 0° and 90° to the specimen (and tensile) axis.

In the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens, there occurred plenty of interaction between the fibers and the matrix. Again, as expected from the analysis referred to above, in these composites the failure occurred by the shear of matrix parallel to the fiber direction. The off angle (θ) composites exhibit shear coupling (6,7) i.e. even when a pure tensile stress is applied to the composite, there results a shear strain and the fibers tend to align parallel to the applied stress direction with the result that the effective θ is reduced. In the cross plied composites this reduction in θ is minimised as the two sets of fibers tend to align parallel to the tensile axis from the opposing directions with the net result that θ is maintained for larger stress values. Thus, the micro voids of irregular shape formed in magnesium assumed the quasi-rectangular form because of shear along mutually orthogonal directions (see Fig.8). With continued stressing these voids were stretched out, joined and formed into cracks which ran parallel to the fibers. Ultimately fracture of the composite occurred by the propagation of these cracks along the fiber directions, as shown in Fig.10.

The comparatively rather large and uniform fracture strain in the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens is thought to be related to the much higher incidence of mechanical twinning in these specimens. The shear of matrix along the two sets of fibers would appear to constrain the matrix to twin, followed by slip on the reoriented basal slip plane. Initial plastic deformation in the magnesium matrix in all the composites would occur by basal slip, but rotation of the glide plane together with constraints from the two sets of fibers in the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens would activate more mechanical twinning in these $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens than in others.

Conclusions

1. In the 0° specimens, where the highest stress levels were obtained, the composite failure occurred in the following manner: increasing fiber breaking in the course of stressing and fiber pull out at these breaking points led to an extreme weakening of a cross section, more or less normal to the tensile axis, and fracture occurred along this cross section.

2. In the 90° specimens, matrix deformation was concentrated in the vicinity of the fibers and the composite failure occurred by decohesion of fiber/matrix interface, followed by tensile failure of the matrix foils. The fracture path was more or less normal to the tensile axis. Very little fiber splitting was observed, i.e. fiber/matrix bonding was far from perfect. Mg/Mg interfaces also opened up occasionally.

3. In the $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ specimens, the fracture path zig-zagged along 0° (where fiber pull out occurred) and 90° (when fiber/matrix decohesion occurred) and the failure modes were a mixture of those indicated in (1) and (2) above. There was practically no interaction between the two sets of fibers.

4. In the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens, matrix shear parallel to the two sets of mutually perpendicular fibers led to composite failure. The fracture path ran either parallel to one set of fibers or part way parallel to one set and part way to the other; while the matrix in between the two sets of fibers suffered extensive tearing due to shear. The comparatively large and uniform extension in the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens is attributed to constraints from the two sets of fibers which led to a greater incidence of twinning in these samples.

5. The effect of fiber orientation on the deformation and fracture behavior of composites is in accord with the formulations made in refs. (2,3).

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Fig.1 - Representative stress strain curves of the four types of composites.

Fig. 2 - A scanning electron micrograph showing the fracture of a 0° specimen. Observe the fiber pull out and a sizeable piece of magnesium matrix adhering to a fiber.

Fig. 3 - A scanning electron micrograph showing rough and jagged Mg matrix surface against which a fiber slid during pull out.

Fig.4a - A scanning electron micrograph of a 90° specimen showing the fiber/matrix debonding and matrix/matrix foil debonding.

Fig.4b - Fiber/matrix interface decohesion and matrix cracking in a 90° specimen. Notice that the matrix adhering to the fiber along a part of its length has caused a crack in the matrix. SEM. (cf. Fig.2).

Fig.5 - A scanning electron micrograph of a $0^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}$ specimen showing the fracture path.

Fig.6 - A scanning electron micrograph of the fracture surface of a $0^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}$ specimen.

Fig.7 - An optical micrograph of a $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen showing the shear in matrix parallel to the fiber. Note the off-set in the two scratch marks. The crack in matrix runs parallel to the fiber direction.

Fig.8 - A scanning electron micrograph of a $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen showing shear of matrix along the two sets of fibers which led to the formation of the characteristic quasi-rectangular void shape.

Fig.9 - Tearing of the matrix in a $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen along the second set of fibers after it has cracked along the first set. SEM.

Fig.10 - A scanning electron micrograph of a $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen showing that the final fracture ran part way parallel to one set of fibers and part way to the other. Note also the fiber pull out.